

Trends of Urbanization in Uttar Pradesh – A Comparative Analysis of 2001-2011

Paper Id : 20550 Submission Date : 2025-08-04 Acceptance Date : 2025-08-22 Publication Date : 2025-08-25

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.17052951

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/innovation.php#8>

Ahmad Eqbal

Associate Professor
Department Of Sociology
P.C. Bagla (PG) College
Hathras, Uttar Pradesh,
India

Abstract

Present paper tries to analyse the trends of urbanization in U.P. while comparing the concerned data of two decades. The researcher undertook several variables like family size literacy rate, sex ratio, birth and death rate employment, migration etc. to analyse the pattern and pace of urbanization in U.P. and to reach on certain concrete conclusion investigator compares the data regarding these variables of two decades in 2001 and 2011. Suitable to the problem undertaken a secondary data based study is suggested. The researcher collected data and information from Census book, National Sample Survey and other government agencies including data provided by Non-governmental organisation also. Present research paper endeavored to explain and interpret the effect of rapid urbanization on different social aspects and social life of people. Time period may appear short but it is a humble attempt to sketch the real picture of social scenario in the area understudy. Descriptive analytical Method is used in this study to draw conclusion which may have much more strong base. Present research work may be helpful to geographers and demographers.

Keywords

Slum, Migration, Population, Census, Urbanization, Employment.

Introduction

Urbanization has been a global phenomenon. It is not confined to metropolis only. Social analysts generally agree with the common sense observation that major social changes that are taking place in the modern world have created and are creating massive shift in social structure throughout the world. Urbanization is one of such important changes. In its popular usages the term urbanization refers to a process whereby a traditionally rural bound community wholly or partially moves to adopt a different pattern of life where activities are primarily centered in Government or manufacture, the process is intimately related with industrialization, westernization and modernization. All these are indices of change in different aspects of society. These concepts apparently look quite synonymous, although differ characteristically in meaning and contents. All these processes encourage migration of people from rural to urban areas for better life and livelihood. People from rural setting flock towards urban centers in search of job and employment which paved the way for the process of urbanization. The researcher in this study compares the data of two decades for the pace of urbanization in Uttar Pradesh.

Objective of study

The main concern of this exercise is basically of academic orientation with a view to help understanding urban life. Present paper focuses on how different of people changes in urban areas with the passage of time. It covers how sex ratio, literacy, density affect the life of urban people. In course of study researcher tries to find out how over population in cities give rise to slum areas leading to alcoholism, prostitution and juvenile delinquency. Rapid pace of urbanization passes challenge of health and hygiene and of course the problem of sanitation also. In Uttar Pradesh, because it is a prosperous and developing state, rural migrants prefer to move towards town and cities in search of livelihood and better life condition and opportunity. The investigator aims to find out the root causes of migration of rural people. And after migration how people settle in urban centers. This study takes into consideration the after effect of migration which create a huge amount of multi-problems in urban areas. Though high rate of urbanization is an indicator of development but it may have certain serious issues challenging the administrator, policy makers and law enforcement system to tackle these down.

Review of Literature

In India before 1960 urban studies are not commonly done. Sociologists like R.K. Mukherjee and G.S. Ghurye have no doubt written on the urban life cities here have mostly been studied by geographers. Dr. A.R. Tiwari (Agra) surveyed the urban regions of Agra. Dr. R.L. Singh (Varanasi) studied the urban geography of Banaras; Dr. Ujagir Singh (Banaras) conducted a comparative study of KAVAL towns of Uttar Pradesh, Dr. R.L. Dwivedi (Allahabad) studied the urban geography of Allahabad. Some other studies were conducted by Dr. Madhusadan Singh (Agra) and Dr. S.P. Mathew (Dehradun) on Meerut and Dehradun respectively. Among Sociologists Dr. Baljit Singh in collaboration with Late Dr. Radha Kamal Mukhrjee, studied Lucknow and Gorakhpur; 'Social Profiles of a

Metropolis' and 'A District Town in Transition'. Another study "Trends of urbanization in Uttar Pradesh" conducted by Mrs. Sudha Saxena has also been published. In 1970 M.S.A. Rao analysed the social change in Indian Villages and explain the impact of urbanization in India in his worth "urbanization and social change." A very valuable work done by Ashish Bose pattern of population change in India 1961 (Bombay) has benefited a lot to urban researcher. Prof. M.S.A. Rao (Delhi) has studied urbanization and social change". An important contribution by Ashish Bose 'changing paradigm' 1991 (Bombay) in the realm of population and urban studies helps the researchers regarding the emerging pattern of population growth and the process of urbanization.

Roy Turnar (d.) 'India's Urban Future' is a valuable work of selected studies on urbanization in India. Ashish Bose (Delhi) has written on the source material of urbanization in India. Prof. M.N. Srinivas and Dr. V.K.R.V. Rao have contributed important articles on industrialization and urbanization. Allen G. Noble and Ashok K. Dutta (ed.) 'Indian Urbanization and Planning' (Delhi) is a good work containing important articles on different aspects of urbanization and planning by distinguished sociologists and demographers of India and abroad. Besides, many articles and paper are contributed in different symposium and conferences. In spite of these studies there is a growing need of further exploration in this field. Particularly in the context of Uttar Pradesh in India there is paucity of urban literature and the scope of urban research here is quite wide.

Methodology

To conduct research work there are several methods of data collection. Looking at the nature of the problem under study a descriptive analytical research design has been suggested. As the descriptive studies portray the characteristics of a particular group, communities or situation so in the present study, a focus is given on the urban population residing within a legally defined territory. It is analytical in approach as we move from macro to micro level for generalization. 'It is a Time Dimension Inquiry' because the variables of family size, density, literacy and migration have been put to analysis on the basis of data collected at two points in time in the same universe. Census data of 2001 and 2011 for U.P. pertaining to above mentioned variables have been collected. It is, therefore, a trend study. It is obvious that in such a time-dimension research there is no way of observing internal changes. As it has already been mentioned, the present study is based on secondary sources of data. These secondary data as we know may be in the form of personal document or public document. In India we have a huge amount of published data. Most of these are generated by central and state governments.

Findings

When use compare the data pertaining to variables undertaken for the study like literacy rate, density of population, sex ratio, female work participation rate, and the rate of urbanization during 2001 and 2011. We find a huge difference and increase in all these perspectives. When we see the literacy rate in U.P. during 2001 its percentage is 56.27% which rose upto 67.7% in 2011. Near about 11.50% marvelous increase had been observed. It may be generalized that effort taken by the government is somewhat successful in the field of education in U.P. Higher the literacy higher the sex ratio because of education people become aware and male child preference has gone down. Consequently sex ratios has gone up. In 2001 sex ratio in U.P. was 89.8 females per thousand males which increased to 912 females per thousand males in 2011. It is a tremendous increase which indicates the thinking of people. It may also be said that government's effort to curb female infanticide is to some extent successful. The population density of U.P. in 2001 was 690 persons per square kilometer which increased to 829 persons per square kilometer in 2011, which is a tremendous increase and an indicator of highly agglomerated urban center. While observing the rate of urbanization in Uttar Pradesh in 2001 only 20.78% of area was urbanized which rose to 22.27% in 2011. Female work participation rate which was 10.82% in 2001 gone upto 17.2% in 2011, which is a huge change in U.P.'s economic system. Females are now more working and contributing in the social development

Conclusion

The researcher after validating the hypotheses which we formulated in the beginning come to the conclusion that in Uttar Pradesh during 2001 and 2011 life standards of people has been upgraded. Through the data provided in the study it may be inferred that with the help of female work participation income of families has gone up and people's possession of articles and the consumption of commodities and their way of expenditure and saving represent them as urban people. So, it may be concluded that with the increase of income people become able to sustain themselves up to the level of urban standard of life which is relatively more expensive. It may also be inferred that due to the expansion of cities surrounding areas called hinterland or suburbs also grow leading to the horizontal urbanization. So, it may be said that smaller adjoining regions to cities also flourish and the filtration approach benefit are received by small towns.

References

1. Gibbs, J.P. (Ed.) "Urban Research Methods," 1961, p. 393.
2. Rao, M.S.A., "Urbanization and Social Change," Orient Longman Ltd., New Delhi, 1970, p. 2.
3. Srinivas, M.N., "Social Changes in Modern India," University of California Press, 1967, p. 48.

4. Davis, K., "The origin and growth of urbanization in the world," A paper in *American Journal of Sociology*, 1955.
5. Bose, Ashish, "Urbanization in India," Academic Book Ltd., New Delhi, 1970, p. 19.
6. *Census of India, Occasional Paper 4 of Literacy Trends.*
7. *India Annual 2011.*
8. *National Sample Survey, data 2001, 2011.*
9. Mukherjee, R.K., "The Indian Working Class," Hind Kitab Ltd., Bombay, 1949, p. 295.
10. Gibbs, J.P. and Martin, W.T., "Urbanization, Technology and the Division of Labour," *American Sociological Review*, 1962, p. 25.